

Mediation Role of Consumer Satisfaction, Consumer Experience, Price Perception, Quality of Service and Brand Image on Repurchasing Interest (Study at Empal Gentong Restaurant H. Apud Cirebon)

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to analyze the role of consumer satisfaction in mediating consumer experience, price perception, service quality and brand image on repurchase intention (case study of Empal Gentong H. Apud). The study involved 151 consumers of empal gentong H. Apud who had bought at least once in three months and were in the Cirebon area. Researchers used Partial Least Square (PLS) as a technique used to analyze measurements and structural models. This type of research is descriptive quantitative with the method used is a direct survey and using google form and the results of this study indicate that three variables have a positive and significant effect while the other five variables have a positive and insignificant effect and the last one has a negative and insignificant effect.

KEYWORDS: Brand Image, Consumer Experience, Consumer Satisfaction and Repurchasing Interest, Price Perception, Service Quality

INTRODUCTION

The corona virus or Covid-19 began on December 31, 2019, starting at the Huanan seafood market, Wuhan city, Hubei province, in China (www.sains.kompas.com) and the start of PSBB carried out by the DKI Jakarta government which carried out large-scale social activities (PSBB) (www.bbc.com). The existence of the Covid-19 pandemic has greatly affected the decline in the MSME sector in Indonesia, especially in the food and beverage sector, which was reported by LIPI in 2020.

The Indonesian Institute of Sciences (LIPI) projects that one of the affected in the tourism sector is Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), especially in the food and beverage business unit. In addition, handicrafts from wood and rattan are business units affected by Covid-19. In the two business units, the scope of micro-enterprises was the most affected, namely as much as 27% of wood and rattan. For information, the total loss from the tourism sector reached US\$ 2 billion with a decrease in aircraft growth by 0.013%, accommodation provision by 0.008% and food and beverage by 0.006%. GAPMMI said the Covid-19 pandemic forced associations to cut sales growth projects for micro businesses from 7% to 4-5% in the food and beverage business unit and 17.03% in handicrafts (www.batamtoday.com).

The Cirebon area itself is divided into two areas, Cirebon city and Cirebon district. And the following is according to BPS data for the city of Cirebon from 2016-2020 the total population in the Cirebon area.

From the regional table above, the population of Cirebon district in 2020 is 2,270.6 and the total population in the city of Cirebon itself is 333.3 and the Empal Gentong that we discussed is in the Cirebon region of West Java.

One of the UMKM in the food unit affected in the culinary field is the culinary business of Empal Gentong H. Apud which causes a decrease in sales turnover. In 2019, before the pandemic period, the average turnover was 15-20 million per day, with the Covid-19 pandemic, the turnover decreased to 5 to 7 million per day. The decline in sales turnover of Empal Gentong H. Apud is very far compared to previous years (www.republika.co.id).

The following is a graph of Empal Gentong H. Apud and Amarta's annual turnover from 2017 - 2020.

Source: Empal Gentong H. Apud and Amarthha

From a survey conducted by researchers to Empal Gentong H. Apud and Amarthha, the average daily turnover has begun to decline before the pandemic as seen from the table data above in 2019 there has been a decline of Rp. 3.6 billion for Empal Gentong H. Apud, and 1.08 billion profit for Empal Gentong Amarthha compared to the previous year and in 2020 coupled with the covid pandemic, annual turnover decreased in 2020 for H. Apud itself decreased to 2.52 billion and for Amrtha of 1.08 billion the same as in 2019 because almost 60% of Empal Gantong H. Apud's visitors came from outside the city and 40% from Cirebon and surrounding areas, and there was a decrease in the need for beef per day before this covid pandemic.

The need for Empal Gentong H. Apud meat before the pandemic could reach 100 kg per day after the pandemic was only 30 kg while Amarthha only 15 kg per day. With the decline in turnover in 2019 and the enactment of the PSBB in 2020, it has greatly reduced visitors and reduced production as well as a very significant decrease in income.

From the picture above, it can be seen that there was a decrease in visitors in 2019 for Empal Gentong H. Apud of 288,000 and Amarthha 27,000. In 2020 there were 201,600 visitors, while Amarthha 21.60 visitors, this proves that before the covid pandemic there has been a decline in visitors annually and coupled with the Covid-19, the number of visitors to Empal Gentong H. Apud and Amarthha has decreased, there needs to be an effort from Empal Gentong H. Apud and Amarthha to attract visitors to repurchase so that sales turnover increases and production increases. According to Adinata and Yasa (2018), the stronger and more positive the brand image that is formed, the more positive the consumer's attitude towards a brand or product. Paramananda and

Sukaatmadja (2018), the better the brand image, the higher the consumer's interest in repurchasing. The customer satisfaction factor also greatly influences consumers to make repeat purchases.

From previous research journals according to Saleem, et al., (2017) service quality affects repurchase interest through brand image channels. Dabbous & Barakat, (2019) services and services have a significant influence and can affect customer satisfaction to become the basis for repurchase decisions and even become customers. Purbasari & Purnamasari (2018) service quality affects satisfaction and satisfaction affects repurchase interest, this means that consumers assess the attitude of service providers as initial expectations regarding performance. Adriani & Warmika (2019) Service quality has a positive and significant effect on repurchase interest mediated by customer satisfaction. Ing et al., (2020) service quality and customer satisfaction can all increase customer repurchase interest. According to Agmeka et al., (2019) the stronger and more positive the brand image that is formed, the more positive the consumer's attitude towards a brand or product. Paramananda & Sukaatmadja (2018), the better the brand image, the higher the consumer's interest in repurchasing. The customer satisfaction factor also greatly influences consumers to make repeat purchases.

According to Savitri & Wardana, (2018) the perceived satisfaction of a performance product can also make consumers recommend the product to others for repurchase interest or repeatedly. Han et al., (2019) stated that customer satisfaction on repurchase intention is considered the best factor influencing customer interest in revisiting. Putri et al., (2015) repurchase interest is the act or desire of consumers to repurchase because of the satisfaction of the products needed by consumers. The researcher concludes that the consumer's desire to repurchase is influenced by satisfaction with a product he bought and experience determines consumers to repurchase. Malik et al., (2012) if customers are satisfied, are more likely to have the desire to repurchase, that is, repeat to buy or recommend others to buy. Parastanti, (20140) a positive attitude developed by consumers as a result of evaluating their consumption experience with a product makes consumers make decisions to repurchase. Saleem et al., (2017) buying interest is influenced by the level of consumer experience. The better the experience obtained by consumers, the greater the chance of interest in making purchases again. A good consumer experience and perceived by consumers is a multisensory stimulated experience. Putri et al., (2015) stated that customers who get more profitable shopping experiences have an interest in repurchasing the product.

According to Chang et al., (2013) price perception is one of the factors considered in consumer decision making both in the first purchase and in repeat purchases. Soliha et al., (2017) fair price is a marketing mix that affects customer satisfaction and repurchase intention

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Schiffman and Kanuk (2008) In general, how consumers behave is influenced by internal factors and external factors. Internal factors are factors that exist in the consumer itself. While external factors are factors that come from outside the consumer itself. Kartikasari, Arifin, Hidayat (2013) factors that influence consumer buying behavior are cultural, social, personal and psychological factors. Khaniwale (2015) buyer behavior is the customer's final decision regarding product choice and brand choice. Auf et al (2018). The factors that influence consumer behavior are divided into two groups, namely external and internal. External factors consist of cultural, social and demographic factors while internal factors contain subjective and psychosomatic factors. However, each individual's purchase decision is inspired by four psychosomatic factors, namely; learning, motivation, perception, and attitude.

And Ariffin et al (2016) consumer assessment of a product can be seen as the emotional value of consumers. Hafifah and Novri, (2018) consumer behavior is defined as a dynamic interaction between affection, cognition, behavior, and the environment in which humans carry out exchange activities in their lives. Yousfi, Lakhrif, Zoubir (2020) satisfaction is a key variable in understanding purchasing behavior. From the research journal above, the researcher concludes that consumer behavior is basically divided into two, namely internal which has consumer factors themselves such as subjective and psychomatic factors and external factors influenced by demography, social and culture, which interact dynamically between affixation, cognition and behavior, to understand consumer behavior.

A. Consumer Behavior

Khaniwale (2015) buyer behavior is the customer's final decision regarding product choice and brand choice. Auf et al (2018) The factors that influence consumer behavior are divided into two groups, namely external and internal. External factors consist of

cultural, social and demographic factors while internal factors contain subjective and psychosomatic factors. However, each individual's purchase decision is inspired by four psychosomatic factors, namely; learning, motivation, perception, and attitude. And Ariffin et al (2016) consumer assessment of a product can be seen as the emotional value of consumers. Hafifah and Novri, (2018) consumer behavior is defined as a dynamic interaction between affection, cognition, behavior, and the environment in which humans carry out exchange activities in their lives. Yousfi, Lakhrif, Zoubir (2020) satisfaction is a key variable in understanding purchasing behavior.

B. Brand Image

Wijaya (2013) revealed that brand image affects the perceived quality of customers and therefore further affects consumers' intention to repurchase. Sallam (2016) has a positive image of their brand in consumers' imagination, meaning that the company creates a positive image of brand value and helps consumers in their choice process. Must be so innovative and creative to ensure that customers can choose their goods if their company is to remain competitive in the market. And According to Robby, Lestari and Andjarwati (2016) brand image is the brand's ability to meet the psychological or social needs of customers. Brand image can be formed directly through the consumer's experience and contact with the product, brand, market, target or usage situation and indirectly through advertising and communication. Furthermore, Venessa and Arifin (2017) state that brand image consists of three supporting components, namely: Corporate Image, Consumer Image, and Product Image.

C. Customer Satisfaction

Amir in Thabrani (2010) Customer satisfaction is the extent to which the benefits of a product are felt in accordance with what the customer expects. And according to Supranto who refers to Tambrin (2010) from the several definitions above, it can be concluded that customer satisfaction is something that is felt by customers after getting results. Achieved from the product on the customer's expectations of the product. From the research journal above, the researcher concludes that customer satisfaction is an evaluation for the company of whether or not it is useful or not given to customers which is reflected in the customer's feelings and behavior after he buys with him to repurchase or not.

D. Service Quality

Marwa and Rohaeni (2018) quality of service is the level of superiority of products and services that are expected over the level of excellence to meet consumer desires. Services will be accepted by consumers if they are as expected. Khattab (2018) quality of service is a major challenge, and there is widespread debate around the correct number of dimensions. Cultural diversity, demographic variables, and personal factors all contribute to variations in service quality dimensions. From the journal above, the researcher concludes that the service quality factor is very important because the higher the service quality, the higher the expected level of product excellence, which in the end customers buy back our products with the quality provided.

E. Consumer Experience

Hendra, Djawahir and Djazuli (2017) customer experience has a significant influence on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Pranoto and Subagio (2017) Customer experience can stimulate customer motivation, thereby increasing the value of products and services. A positive customer experience can encourage the creation of an emotional bond between the company's brand and customers which in turn increases customer loyalty because they are satisfied with the company's performance. Yolandari and Kusumadewi (2018) by building a positive experience, it will not only have an impact on customer satisfaction, but can bring a greater impact in the form of creating repurchase interest. From the journal research above, the researcher concludes that consumer experience can build customer loyalty and stimulate customer motivation which in turn will increase customer loyalty which has a greater impact on encouraging the customer to repurchase.

F. Price Perception

Soliha (2017) Price perception is the value contained in a price related to the benefits of owning or using a product or service. Poluakan, Tewal, and Tawas (2017) Pricing is the most crucial and difficult of the elements in the retail marketing mix (merchandise, promotions, in-store atmosphere, prices, and retail services) and price is the price mix with respect to strategy and tactics such as price levels, discount structures, payment terms, and levels of price discrimination among various customer groups.

G. Repurchase Intention

Repurchase interest is the desire and action of consumers to repurchase a product, because of the satisfaction received according to what is desired from a product. Setyorini, and Nugraha (2016) when consumers get positive responses to past actions, there will be a strengthening of positive thoughts to make repurchases. Repurchase intention is the desire and action of consumers to repurchase a product, because there is satisfaction with what consumers need from a product. Journaiti, Rahman and Hafsanudin (2017) Repurchase is a level of motivation for a consumer to repeat the buying behavior of a product, one of which is indicated by the sustainable use of a product's brand.

H. Research framework

The concept of repurchase interest analysis can be seen in the following framework.

I. Hypothesis

- Consumer experience has a positive and significant direct effect on the repurchase intention of Empal Gentong H. Apud.
- Consumer experience has a positive and significant effect on repurchase interest which is mediated by customer satisfaction Empal Gentong H. Apud
- Price perception has a positive and significant direct effect on the repurchase intention of Empal Gentong H. Apud
- Price perception has a positive and significant effect on repurchase interest which is mediated by Empal Gentong H. Apud customer satisfaction.
- Service quality has a direct positive and significant effect on the repurchase intention of Empal Gentong H. Apud
- Service quality has a positive and significant effect on repurchase interest mediated by customer satisfaction Empal Gentong H. Apud
- Brand image has a positive and significant direct effect on repurchase interest.
- Brand image has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention mediated by customer satisfaction Empal Gentong H. Apud
- Customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the repurchase intention of Empal Gentong H. Apud

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses descriptive quantitative methods. This research analyzes and collects data based on primary data by direct surveys to the place of Empal Gentong H. Apud and secondary data that can be from the web or by distributing questionnaires to consumers of Empal Gentong H. Apud who have purchased at least once. in three months and this research began with a decrease in sales turnover before the covid 19, coupled with the Covid-19 pandemic so that there was a PSBB and caused a decline in the MSME sector, especially the culinary empal gentong H. Apud in Cirebon.

According to Sekaran & Bougie (2019) purposive sampling is a sampling technique based on certain characteristics, namely characteristics that have something to do with the characteristics and characteristics of the population.

According to Wahyu et al (2018) which refers to Hair et al (2010) the number of samples cannot be factored if the number is less than 50, the sample must be 100 or more As a general rule, the minimum sample size is at least 5 times and will be more acceptable if the number of samples is 10 times the number of variables to be studied and analyzed, the sample is taken using purposive sampling method. For the number of samples used and the number of samples used in this study are: Number of samples = 26 x 5 = 130 respondents.

This study uses the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) data analysis method and uses the Smart-PLS (Partial Least Square) program with measurement model and structural model tests. According to Boonsiritomachai & Pitchayadejanant (2019) Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is an analytical technique applied to test hypotheses and detect linkages between independent variables and dependent variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Test Results

Analysis of the results of the outer model test carried out, among others:

- 1) Convergent validity (outer loading)

From the results of data processing with SmartPLS version 3.3.3, it shows that all variable indicators of customer satisfaction, service quality, brand image, price perception, consumer experience and repurchase interest have a loading value greater than 0.5 which indicates the correlation between constructs has a level of validity. which is quite high. Thus the analysis continued.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusions

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) Brand image has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction, this shows that the better the popularity of Empal Gentong H. Apud will increase customer satisfaction, this means that the better the Empal Gentong brand image, the higher customer satisfaction or the worse the Empal Gentong brand image, the better low customer satisfaction.
- 2) Brand image has a positive but not significant effect on repurchase interest, this shows that if Empal Gentong H. Apud has poor product quality, it will reduce customer interest in repurchasing Empal Gentong H. Apud.
- 3) Price perception has a positive but not significant effect on customer satisfaction, this shows that the price offered by Empal Gentong H. Apud is still in accordance with consumer purchasing power (reasonable) but has not provided satisfaction to customers

- 4) Price perception has no significant negative effect on repurchase intention, this means that the price of Empal Gentong H. Apud offered still has not attracted customers to be interested in repurchasing
- 5) Service quality has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction, this shows that the responsive service from Empal Gentong H. Apud is able to increase customer satisfaction, the better the quality of service provided, the more consumers are interested in buying back Empal Gentong H. Apud.
- 6) Service quality has a significant positive effect on repurchase interest, this shows that the service friendliness of Empal Gentong H. Apud employees to customers who come will increase consumer interest in coming to buy again,
- 7) Customer satisfaction has a significant positive effect on repurchase interest, the usefulness factor of the product obtained by consumers is an aspect of satisfaction that can increase consumer interest in buying back Empal Gentong H. Apud.
- 8) Consumer experience has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction, has a good relationship with consumers which is an aspect of consumer experience that will increase consumer interest in repurchasing Empal Gentong H. Apud.
- 9) Consumer experience has a significant positive effect on repurchase interest, the factor of good relations with consumers is an aspect of consumer experience that will increase consumer interest in repurchasing empal gentong H. Apud.

B. Suggestion

Researchers suggest for further research (academic) who are interested in discussing variables. The value of r-square explains the variability of the customer satisfaction construct of 67.6% and the remaining 32.4.0% is explained by other constructs outside those studied in this study. Furthermore, repurchase interest was able to explain the variability of the construct of 67.9.3% and the remaining 32.1% was explained by other constructs outside those studied in this study. The larger the R-square number indicates the greater the independent variable can explain the dependent variable so that the better the structural equation, which means that further researchers need to re-examine this research model by involving other variables related to the use of technology, it also needs to be investigated further in other application models.

Further researchers also need to do a more comprehensive explanation by making related comparisons based on customer satisfaction as well as psychological factors on their influence on repurchase interest.

Practical Advice

Based on the results of the study, the researchers suggest to Empal Gentong H. Apud business actors and culinary food providers to pay attention to several things related to customer satisfaction that affect repurchase interest as follows Empal Gentong H. Apud business actors need to consider customer satisfaction factors in entertaining customers, improve the image that satisfies customers and the quality of service is even better, the goal is for customers to come to buy again and feel satisfied with the services provided by Empal Gentong H. Apud.

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